

PERCEPTION OF CUSTOMERS AND THEIR BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS DIGITAL MARKETING WITH REFERENCE TO ODISHA STATE

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Cite This Article: Sanjay Kumar Barik, "Perception of Customers and their Behaviour towards Digital Marketing with Reference to Odisha State", International Journal of Computational Research and Development, Volume 6, Issue 2, Page Number 13-18, 2021.

Abstract:

The study started with the aim to analyse the various problems involving the digital marketing. Supported the discussion it's been found that just in case of the digital selling the foremost vital facet is to attach with the users. The ladder of engagement has shown the approaches to connect with the customers. The study has additionally unconcealed that so as to utilize the digital selling in an effective way; the businesses are needed to style an efficient platform. The effectiveness of a social media platform has been discussed. This trends in the digital selling have additionally been mentioned within the study. It has shown that within the current context, it's become vital to integrate all the systems thereupon of the digital platform. It's given State wide scope to understand the selling methods offered and also the most involving digitally involved.

Key Words: Perception, Digital Marketing and Behaviour.

Introduction:

Digital marketing has given us great ways to protect and build our digital reputations. Today they have the ease of searching conversations, the ability to set alerts to help us monitor our names, the constant availability of learning opportunities and more ways to communicate and interact with others. All of these tools, which were not available just a few years ago, now make it possible for us to be proactive in maintaining, building and protecting your personal brand and help spread word-of-mouth about our books.

Fausser et al. (2011) comes up different perception that the digital networks are best suitable only for the communication and information sharing. Only few networks are suits for marketing purpose rest are not a appropriate tool for marketing. The major use fo digital networks are communication only [Fausser et al.2011].

According to Gummesson [2002] through Digital networks made easier the frequent communication, so it play vital role in the initial communication between the business and the customer. Once they connect each other it builds a strong bond in the relationship.

Janal (1998) on the other hand, the business can create brand community page and start discussion with the staffs, friends, and relatives, this will lead to vocal member participation and furthermore it develops the relationship with the member and the brand. This communication between the brand and the online customer can able to understand the product and services provided by brand and became loyal customer for the brand. So this will illustrate us without the information sharing and initial conversation about the brand, there is no possibility for the serious engagement for the brand.

Marketing Through Digital Marketing:

Digital marketing has changed the way people connect, discover, and share information. Digital marketing is the technology that connects people whether it's to share content or just to chat. Digital networks, like Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Pinterest are the places where digital interactions happen (discovering & sharing). Digital marketing is the way to use that technology to build relationships, drive repeat business. And attract new customers through friends sharing with friends. Chadwick Martin Bailey Consumer Pulse 2010 (n= 2204).

In wider conditions the topic of the analysis is group press as a system of promotion and creating item attention, but it is first essential to determine the terminology "marketing" known to in the title. Therefore according to the, The America Marketing Organization, Marketing is an organizational function and a set of techniques for creating, communicating, and offering value to clients and for managing customer connections in techniques that benefit the company and its stakeholders.

In the above, the look for conditions are "organizational function, and techniques for creating, communicating, offering, and exchanging unique provides that have value for customers". From a company perspective, the factors of these techniques known in the importance above are item attention, promotion, etc. Therefore for the sake of this analysis, they focus only on one branch of promotion which is item attention or item management as a process of communicating or offering value to clients as already proven in the value of promotion by The America Marketing Organization Chaffey et al. (2003) thus explain internet promotion as use of the Internet and appropriate digital particular development to achieve promotion objectives (Chaffey et al. 2003, 1). These promotion objectives can be observed by use of Digital networks.

Digital networking techniques provide as a proper tool for promoters (Qualman 2010: 28). What this means is that Facebook, twitter etc. are indicates of accomplishing promotion models through the worldwide web. It is therefore imperative for promoters to find appropriate techniques to suite their promotion objectives.

An outstanding promotion objective allows marketers to acquire new clients, while retaining the already current ones through customer support.

Further evaluation 3 points on how the worldwide web can be used to achieve the „processes“

- Determining how the Internet can be used for promotion analysis to find out customers“ needs and wants
- Anticipating the on the internet earnings contribution
- Client support through digital channel; satisfaction here represents the website simple us ability, adequate performance, and determining what the standard associated customer support is.

Online advertising has an excess of strengths; the speed of accessing information is very fast and very economical, besides that on the internet has no geographical limitations. Moreover to affordability, the professional likewise has to be able to analysis new suppliers at a fraction of past look for expenses. In other conditions all the marketing analysis performed through on the internet is very affordable [Gay et al. 2007, 129]. However are quick to indicate some essential weakness that internet promotion encounter. The first issue is that cultural and language differences may current issues in information gathering across world limitations. Secondly, it can be difficult to assurance that the individual responding is the individual that the customer thinks they are [Gay et al.2007, 129].

Statement of the Problem:

This includes the parameters that are based on the strength/weakness of the organization that holds the overview about the challenges that are expected to be dealt. This methodology is important to know about the needs of the organization to develop their organization growth level and to it may vary from time to time based on the priority. To identify the shortfalls of the organization and to rectify the process. This system explains about the digital marketing process that is to be integrated with various departments to increase the position of the sector.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study on the digital marketing in Odisha
- To study about the importance of digital marketing in the current trend
- To know the other marketing strategies involved in uniq.
- To understand the effectiveness of marketing in retaining the relationship with customers
- To study about the advantages and disadvantages of digital marketing
- To understand the challenges involved in implementing the marketing via digitally

Need of the Study:

- To develop an intelligent appreciation of modern marketing practices.
- To develop guiding policies regarding marketing procedures and their implementation.
- To analyze marketing problems according to circumstances and to make solution.
- To study the shortcoming in the existing patterns of marketing.
- To enable managers to assess and decide a particular course of action

Scope of the Study:

- Studying various marketing strategies
- Interacting with the employees of the company
- We got to know why customer retention is important in every business
- Knowing the digital marketing in the current trends

Research Design:

Research design refers to the overall structure and orientation of an investigation. A descriptive research design was carried out to study the digital marketing techniques followed in Odisha.

Population:

The aggregate of all the units concerning this study is called “population”. The population for this study is 150 respondents.

Sampling Technique:

The Sampling technique used in this study is simple random sampling. Simple random sampling is a method used to call a smaller sample size from a larger population and use it to research and make generalizations about the larger group.

Sample Size:

Sample size is the act of choosing the number of respondents. Sample size they focus on this project is 150 respondents were taken from the population by using random sampling method.

Sample Design:

Sampling design is imperative in every scientific study. Hence in this study simple random sampling methods have been used to collect data.

Sampling Tools:

Percentage analysis, Kruskal-Wallis test and One way-Anova.

Limitations of the Study:

- The sample size of the study is limited to 150.
- There may be a bias towards primary data collected from the respondents.
- The sampling is limited to a specific area.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Demographic Variables	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Age	20-25 yrs	24	16
	26-30 yrs	53	35.3
	31-35 yrs	63	42
	More than 35	10	6.66
	Total	150	99.96
Gender	Male	97	64.6
	Female	53	35.3
	Total	150	99.9
Income level	Less than 2 lakhs	13	8.66
	2.01 -3 lakhs	51	34
	3-4 lakhs	64	42.6
	More than 4 lakhs	22	14.6
	Total	150	100
Year of experience	Less than a year	23	15.3
	1-2 years	68	45.3
	2-3 years	39	26
	More than 3 years	20	13.3
	Total	150	100

From the analysis can see that the male respondent percentage is 64.6% and the female is 35.3%.64.6% and the female is 35.3%.42.6% has a income level of 3-4 Lakhs. The major respondents of 34% has income level of 2.01-3 lakhs and the lowest respondents of 8.66% has income level less than 2 lakhs.45.3% has a experience level of 1-2 years and the lower respondents of 13.3% has experience level of more than 3 years.36% find marketing as reachability.

Perception of Respondents towards Marketing:

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Promotion	38	25.3
Awareness of the brand	37	24.6
Reachability	54	36
Business making	21	14
Total	150	100

From the analysis can see that the major respondents of 36% find marketing as reachability. The respondents of 24.6% find marketing as awareness of the brand. The respondents of 25.3% find marketing as promotion and the remaining respondents of 14% find marketing as business making.

Main Marketing Strategies Generating Business:

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Online Marketing	29	19.3
Facebook Marketing	45	30
Telemarketing	53	35.3
Direct Marketing	23	15.3
Total	150	99.9

From the analysis can see that the major respondents of 35.3% has selected telemarketing as the main marketing strategies. The respondents of 30% has selected facebook marketing as the main marketing strategies and the remaining respondents of 34.6% has selected online and direct marketing strategies.

Prefer Using Digital Marketing for Business:

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Yes	79	52.6
No	14	9.33
Sometimes	57	38
Total	150	100

From the analysis can see that the respondents of 52.6% prefer digital marketing for business needs. The respondents of 38% sometimes prefer digital marketing and the remaining 9.33% do not prefer digital marketing for business.

One Way Anova:

Comparison between Age and Acceptance of Respondents towards Digital Marketing:

Ho1: There is a significant difference between age and acceptance of respondents towards digital marketing

Descriptive:

Acceptance	Age	N	Mean	SD	F	Sig
Business emerged via digital marketing	20-25 years	24	2.33	.963	0.129	0.043
	26-30 years	53	2.36	.901		
	31-35 years	63	2.32	.800		
	More than 35	10	2.50	1.080		
	Total	150	2.35	.875		
Marketing team strategies support for business growth	20-25 years	24	2.04	.751	1.626	0.186
	26-30 years	53	2.15	.886		
	31-35 years	63	2.30	.873		
	More than 35	10	2.70	1.059		
	Total	150	2.23	.878		
Marketing the respondents in retaining their clients	20-25 years	24	2.67	.702	.116	.951
	26-30 years	53	2.70	.911		
	31-35 years	63	2.75	.842		
	More than 35	10	2.60	.966		
	Total	150	2.71	.848		

It reveals that age has no significant difference with business emerged via digital marketing (0.043) and meanwhile, age has a significant difference with Marketing team strategies support for business growth (0.186) and Marketing the respondents in retaining their clients (0.951).

Business Emerged Via Digital Marketing:

The respondents who are from the age group between 20-25 (2.33), age group between 26-30 (2.36), between 31-35 (2.32), and more than 35 (2.50) agree towards business emerged via digital marketing.

Kruskall Wallis Test:

Comparison between Gender and Acceptance of Respondents towards Digital Marketing:

Ho2: There is a significant difference between gender and acceptance of respondents towards digital marketing

Ranks:

Particulars	Gender	N	Mean Rank	Chi-square	Sig
Business emerged via digital marketing	Male	97	73.11	0.963	0.326
	Female	53	79.88		
	Total	150			
Marketing team strategies support for business growth	Male	97	73.08	1.125	0.002
	Female	53	79.93		
	Total	150			
Marketing the respondents in retaining their clients	Male	97	75.01	0.042	0.838
	Female	53	76.40		
	Total	150			

There is no relationship between gender and business emerged via digital marketing (0.326) and Marketing the respondents in retaining their clients (0.838). Meanwhile, there is a relationship between gender and marketing team strategies support for business growth (0.002).

Marketing Team Strategies Support for Business Growth:

It reveals that the respondents who are female (79.93) have higher level of acceptance towards digital marketing.

Findings:

- From the analysis can see that the major respondents falls in the category of 31-35 yrs of 42% and the least percentage category is 10% of more than 35 yrs.

- From the analysis can see that the male respondent percentage is 64.6% and the female is 35.3%.
- From the analysis can see that the major respondents of 42.6% has a income level of 3-4 Lakhs.
- The major respondents of 34% has income level od 2.01-3 lakhs and the lowest respondents of 8.66% has income level less than 2 lakhs.
- From the analysis can see that the major respondents of 45.3% has a experience level of 1-2 years and the lower respondents of 13.3% has experience level of more than 3 years.
- From the analysis can see that the major respondents of 36% find marketing as reachability.
- The respondents of 24.6% find marketing as awareness of the brand. The respondents of 25.3% find marketing as promotion and the remaining respondents of 14% find marketing as business making.
- From the analysis can see that the major respondents of 35.3% has selected telemarketing as the main marketing strategies. The respondents of 30% has selected facebook marketing as the main marketing strategies and the remaining respondents of 34.6% has selected online and direct marketing strategies.
- From the analysis can see that the respondents of 52.6% prefer digital marketing for business needs. The respondents of 38% sometimes prefer digital marketing and the remaining 9.33% do not prefer digital marketing for business.
- From the analysis can see that the respondents of 72.6% prefer digital marketing for to reach phases where internet is not involved and some prefer both. The respondents of 27.3% prefer to reach via digital channels.
- From the analysis can see that the main digital marketing that is used is social media marketing 27.3% and the second one is content marketing around 26% and the remaining 10% used is the email marketing.

Suggestion and Recommendation:

- Focus on client engagement: Note when and the way typically your customers connect with you and your messages, so create a method that revolves around those key engagement times.
- Develop a transparent knowledge strategy: Consider the client interaction knowledge you presently have and can acquire within the future, and develop a long methodology for collection that knowledge to higher analyse differing client engagement times.
- Roll out responsive design: After observing what number of your customers read your emails on their mobile device, determine whether or not utilizing a responsive style set up can enable you to realize a ROI.
- Hone in on clear objectives: Have set, quantitative goals for observation your social media selling plans and then you may be able to additional simply determine what must be modified or additional within your content and client service initiatives.
- Take a deep explore however customers are presently experiencing your brand: Observe how customers are interacting together with your whole each on-line and offline, so produce a replacement plan.
- Start with your customers: Although they have a tendency to board a dominantly digital world, it does not mean that they should always speak like robots on the web. it's become important to check knowledge that's involving customers' behaviour regarding your brand, so develop additional high-quality personalised messages to send them.
- Think regarding personalization beyond email: Aside from personalised emails, businesses are also making full personalised internet interactions. supported the success of your email selling efforts, you ought to develop identical distinctive expertise through varied channels, together with social, mobile and therefore the web.

Conclusion:

The effectiveness of a social media platform has been discussed. This trends in the digital selling have additionally been mentioned within the study. It has shown that within the current context, it's become vital to integrate all the systems thereupon of the digital platform. It's given State wide scope to understand the selling methods offered and also the most involving digitally involved.

References:

1. Aahmedaudumaiyaki, Sanysanurimohd mokhtar (2016) "Correlates of consumer online buying behaviour" Volume-2, Issue-1, Special Issue-1, Pp 12-19.
2. Abdul BashiruJibril, Michael AduKwarteng, Michal Pilik, Elsamari Botha and Christian Nedu Osakwe 2 (2020)" Towards Understanding the Initial Adoption of Online Retail Stores in a Low Internet Penetration Context: An Exploratory Work in Ghana", Pp 1-19.
3. Abdulghader. A. Ahmed, Hadya. S. Hawedi (2012)," Online Shopping and the Transaction Protection in E Commerce: A case Of Online Purchasing in Libya", Volume 2, Issue 6, Pp 1-4.
4. Adi Anuar Azmin, Universiti Malaysia Perlis (2018)" consumer acceptance of trustworthy ecommerce: an extension of technology acceptance model", Volume 17, Issue 6 Pp 1-13.

5. Adil Bashir (2013) "Consumer behavior towards online shopping of electronics in Pakistan", Pp 1-60.
6. Aelita Skaržauskienė, Živilė Baubonienė and Gintarė Gulevičiūtė (2015) "Factors Influencing Consumers Online Shopping Decision: Present and Future Evidence from Lithuania" Pp 301 – 313.
7. Aishah Arshad, Maira Zafar, Iffat Fatima, Shaista Kamal Khan (2015) "The Impact of Perceived Risk on Online Buying Behavior" Volume-1, Issue-8, Pp 13-18.
8. Alina Stankevich (2017) "Explaining the Consumer Decision-Making Process: Critical Literature Review" Volume 2, Issue 6, 2017 Pp 1-8.
9. Amit Bhatnagar, Sanjog Misra, H. Raghav Rao (2000), "On Risk, Convenience, and Internet Shopping Behavior" Vol. 43, Pp 98-105.
10. Amresh Kumar, Bhawna Anjaly (2017) "How to measure post-purchase customer experience in online retailing? A scale development study" Pp 1-23.
11. Amy i. wright, butler university mentor: hongjiangxu (2016), "security risk and social presence in e-commerce", Pp 1-36.
12. Anam Bhatti¹, Dr. Shahrin Saad², Dr. Salimon Maruf Gbadebo³ (2018), "The Effect of Financial Risk and Convenience Risk on Online Shopping Behavior with the Moderating Role of Trust" Vol. 2 Issue 8, Pp 38-42.
13. Anil Bilgihan, Jay Kandampully and Tingting (Christina) Zhang (2015) "Towards a unified customer experience in online shopping environments Antecedents and outcomes" Pp 102 – 121.
14. Antonina Bauman¹ and Reinhard Bachmann² (2017) "Online Consumer Trust: Trends in Research Antonina Bauman¹ and Reinhard Bachmann²", Volume 12, Issue 2 Pp 68-75.
15. Antonina Bauman and Reinhard Bachmann² (2017) "Online Consumer Trust: Trends in Research", Volume 12, Issue 2 Pp 1-12
16. Aron O' Cass^a, Jamie Carlson^{b,c,1} (2011) "An e-retailing assessment of perceived website-service innovativeness: Implications for website quality evaluations, trust, loyalty and word of mouth", Pp 28–36.
17. Arun Aggarwal and Ran Singh (2016), Exploring the Nomological Network of organizational citizenship Behaviour: A review of Dimensions, Antecedents and consequences, IUP Journal of organizational Behaviour, Vol XV, No.3, Pp- 17 – 37.
18. Aswalha Ppa K (1996), organizational behaviour, Third Revised Himalaya Publishing house, Bombay, India, PP 140 - 141.
19. Aswalha Ppa K (1996), organizational behaviour, Third Revised Himalaya Publishing house, Bombay, India, PP 140 – 141
20. Bashur, R. M., Hernandez, A. ve Peiro, J. M. 2011. The Impact of Underemployment on Individual and Organizational Performance.
21. Bateman, T.S., & Organ, D.W. (1983). Job satisfaction and the good soldier: the relationship between affect and citizenship. *Academy of Management Journal*, 26, 587-595.
22. Bing Xu and Jianhui Chen (2017), "Consumer Purchase Decision- Making Process Based on the Traditional Clothing Shopping Form" Vol: 5 Issue: 3 PP 1-12.
23. Bolon, DS 1997, Organizational citizenship behavior among hospital employees: a multidimensional analysis involving job satisfaction and organizational commitment *Hospital & Health Service Administrative*, Vol.42, Pp. 221-41
24. C. Raghunath¹, Mridula Sahay² (2018) "Consumer Behaviour in Online Retail in India" PP 16-19.
25. Charlene Gerber, Shannon Ward, Leila Goedhals -Gerber (2014) "The impact of perceived risk on on-line purchase behaviour" Volume 4, Issue 4, 2014, Pp 99-106.
26. Coleman VI and Borman W C (2000), "Investigating the underlying structure of the citizenship performance domain," *Human Resource Management Review*, Vol.10, 25 – 44.
27. Cunningham P., & Iles, P. (2002). "Managing learning climates in a financial services organization". *Journal of Management Development*, 21, (5/6), Pp477-492.
28. Daniel Ofori¹ and Christina Appiah-Nimo² (2019) "Determinants of online shopping among tertiary students in Ghana: An extended technology acceptance model", Pp 1 -20.
29. David Gefen, Detmar Straub (2000) "The Relative Importance of Perceived Ease of Use in IS Adoption: A Study of E-Commerce Adoption", Volume 1, Article 8 Pp 1-31.
30. Debasis Ghosh (2014) "Why Indian E-Retailing Market is Still a Partly Success and a Partly Failure Story?", Pp 1-6.
31. Dongwon Lee, Jinsoo Park, Joongho Ahn (2000) "on the explanation of factors affecting e-commerce adoption", Pp 1-23.
32. Dr. Hemanth Kumar. S. Dr. Umakanth. September (2018) "influence of e-commerce on buying behaviour of customers" S Volume - 6, Issue- 9, Pp 1-8.
33. Dr. Madhu Bala (2018) "A Critical Review of Digital Marketing "Vol. 8 Issue 10, October Pp 1-20.